

Religious Networks in Late Babylonian Period (RelNet)

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The aim of RelNet, a newly launched project (*), is to generate knowledge about religious networks in Babylonia during the first millennium BCE using cuneiform documents as a basis. Texts of different kinds from both institutional and private archives and libraries contain a wealth of information on religiously motivated movements and on their participants, venues and itineraries. These sacred journeys created multiple ties between sanctuaries, cities... (nods & hubs) and divine and human participants, which link the hubs and nodes. In RelNet, religious networks entail connections between sanctuaries, gods, cultic equipment, temple personnel and participants in the ceremonies. These ties can operate in multiple scales, either in the same temple (movements in the course of a specific temple ceremony), in the same city (processions from one temple to another taking place in open spaces), or on a larger scale, between different cities within Babylonia (e.g. visiting deities and the personnel from their temples spending time in the city of Babylon on the occasion of important annual ceremonies such as the New Year Festival, etc.). Bearing in mind that not all religious ceremonies and movements had the same political/religious significance, each text considered will be "labelled" according to the type of festivity or ritual described in it.

As demonstrated by previous studies focusing on other regions and periods (Malkin 2011; McCorriston 2011; Collar 2013; Rutherford 2013), the analysis of cultic journeys is crucial to elucidate the social function of festivals and religious venues and to analyse the spatial dimension of rituals. I would add that this analysis is also fundamental to study the political implications of religious movements. Recent research has shown that social network analysis (SNA) in the study of religious phenomena is helpful to proceed beyond essentialist viewpoints towards more relational, contextual and multifaceted perspectives (Blake 2013; Knappert 2013; Knappert 2016). However, as some authors have noticed (Rutherford 2013: 9), the most important limitation of the "network" approach is the difficulty of representing the power relations and hierarchies that exist in religious networks. Nevertheless, if we turn from "abstract" SNA to a more concrete, spatially (in the sense of physical, not only social space) oriented approach which also considers the sociomaterial dimension of the network, we can get round this limitation. Indeed, the itineraries, direction and frequency of the movements and the number of links between them are crucial to elucidate the relative position of hubs and nodes. In addition, given that the ties operate in space and involve the movements of people, deities (their statues) and equipment from one place to another, the spatial approach of network analysis is fundamental, for it enables the mapping out of religious itineraries and the spatial organization of the cult. It is also necessary to understand networks as heterogeneous, so we can fully appreciate the multiplicity of relations and the material dimension of religious connections. Issues related to time scale and incompleteness of the textual data will also be considered. For these reasons, an indispensable part of the project is integrating geospatial information with SNA: all geographical information will be collected, organized, analysed and shared in a series of interactive maps built using a geographic information system (GIS), with the aim of obtaining a geospatial SNA. In order to do so, a database with all the information on the networks will be created on the basis of the documentary evidence referred to above (a corpus of approximately 500 texts), and the festivals and religious journeys will be scrutinized using different digital tools: Recogito, yEd, Filemaker, QGIS and Nodegoat. It should be noted that the linguistic structure of Akkadian does not allow for automatic data collection, so it is necessary to sift, with a more traditional approach, the information to be understood in the dataset.

From a methodological point of view, our project will take the following steps:

a) First we will input and catalogue the cuneiform texts and their metadata in the annotation platform Recogito, assigning units of topography (UTs) and actors (Acs) and establishing the relationships between.

b) Then we will export the Recogito data by .csv and import it into the graph editor yEd to obtain a graphical representation of the UTs, Acs and their relationships in the form of diagrams.

c) We will also export the Recogito data by .csv and import it into the Filemaker database. Although it is our aim to use open research tools, none of the available open source databases seems to be as powerful as FM for our purposes.

d) From FM we will choose between two avenues to pursue:

- exporting the FM database to Nodegoat or
- exporting the FM database to QGIS.

In either case we will obtain a representation of the UTs and Acs and their relationships within a geospatial context. Also, the decision to choose one tool or the other will be made in the early stages of the project, since we do not wish to change the tools halfway through the project. Accordingly, we will first run several tests to determine which solution best meets our needs.

e) Lastly, as the final results will be open source, the FM data will be transferred to Omeka.

The main research lines of RelNet are:

- to identify patterns in the articulation of sacred movements or journeys, focusing on cultic topography and the relationships between different nodes and hubs in the resulting networks
- to provide data on the topography of worship in Babylonia, and on the contacts between different hubs and nodes
- to describe the relationships between the axes, their direction and regularity, and their possible modifications through time, identifying their causes
- to analyse the dynamics of cultic journeys in order to elucidate the social function of festivals and places of worship
- to clarify the extent of royal euergetism and its impact on religious networks.

The use of different digital tools and open access visualization platforms will enlarge the spectrum of approaches in the study of religious movements and enable a better visualization and broader dissemination of the results to stakeholders, including the scientific and academic community as well as the general public.

** RelNet started in February 2024. The project website is currently under development (March 2024) and will be partially accessible at the time of the conference (July 2024), when its various contents and some preliminary results (including images and maps) will be shown.*

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